

Career Management for College Teachers

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Amirtha, J. "Career Management for College Teachers." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 125-27.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451647>

Dr. J. Amirtha, M.Com, M.Phil, MBA, Ph.D.,

Associate Professor in Commerce

NMS.Sermathai Vasam College for Women

Avaniyapuram, Madurai

Introduction

Career management is a lifelong process of involving resources to accomplish your future career goals. It is a continuing process that allows you to adapt to the changing demands of our dynamic economy. The career management process embraces various concepts, self-awareness, career development planning or career exploration, lifelong learning, and networking.

Career Management for College Teachers

A teacher's engagement towards a child is probably more than that of the parents. This is primarily because the child doesn't receive education from the school where he or she studies, but also learns the value rules from the same personalities.

For taking up instruction as a career, you require a passion for interchanging ideas, whether it is coaching at a school or in a college. In a college atmosphere, the exchanges are at an intellectual level with students who are your friends.

Eligibility Criteria for Teaching Career in India

The teaching profession is a highly specific field and requires complete training to gain expertise in the area, for some reason, teaching is considered pure and natural to do. There are amazing myths and incorrect generalizations that exist about the tutoring career.

It is ordinarily believed that anyone can teach provided he has some knowledge for the subject nothing could be further from the truth. Experience is just one thing that a teacher should have, among other things. The fundamental qualities required are excellent communication skills, the ability to hold the attention of young minds, to inspire confidence, and finally the ability to set an example by word and deed.

Teaching is one of the tremendous altruistic professions. We join it to help others

To nurture their talents to overcome the disadvantage of their backgrounds, and to share with them our joyful love of learning. We

grow as teachers as we become more successful at helping our students and yet the recognized career pathways in our profession take us, in general, further away from the reason we joined in the first place.

The available possibilities for educators are in a category of topics such as English, Mathematics, science, social studies, etc., The desire for good teachers is substantial considering that today’s children are expected to the internet and the information overflow.

To start a career as an instructor in colleges, you may, however, need to take access reviews along with completing your master’s degree and Ph.D.

Teachers Can Act as a Navigator

Teachers can conduct regular questionings and interactive sessions hardly. This will generate interest of studies among seniors and will provide them a thorough knowledge of the topics covered. Teachers should also focus regularly on general education and current affairs not as a subject, but as an additional ingredient. This will create among the students and will develop a habit of receiving about daily accidents.

Conscientious teachers can guide their students properly right from the opening stage. They can educate them about the nuances of arranging for competing exams and so on. Also, teachers should teach the followers to be anxious and should train them to realize their talent and develop themselves accordingly.

Teachers can make them to face the stiff challenges of the competing world and can give them an idea about various occupations and their importance. Students can be confused about career options and may also be afraid to make the right decisions. At such a time, teachers can guide them to the right career path.

Lecturers/college teachers hold a Ph.D. in the subject. Their work details are :

1. Lecturing students.
2. Researching and preparing for lectures and practical’s.
3. Conducting seminars or tutorials for a small group of students.
4. Setting and marking assignments and exams.
5. Monitoring work projects and placements.
6. Handling students admissions, curriculum development examiner ship.

Skills Needed For College Teachers

1. Inspiring personality
2. Good communication skills
3. Self-confidence
4. Tact and patience
5. Relevant work experience
6. Knowledge of subject.
7. The ability to develop a connection with their students.
8. Engaging students in learning.
9. Dedication to teaching

Overcome the Classroom Challenges

- Lack of empathy, teamwork, and support between students
- Professors working too many roles at the same time
- No time to deal with bodily functions.
- Teachers being made accountable for longer than they should

- Not enough time plan
- Excessive paperwork for data collection
- Keeping up with the assumption of school admins

Six things that Make College Teachers Successful

- Study the knowledge base of learning and teaching
- Accept all who enter the classroom door
- Plan for instructional management
- Teach with a variety of strategies
- Use evaluation to inform students of their attainment
- Keep the passion

Conclusion

As instructors, we have the unique opportunity to help students explore future career opportunities. Research has shown the importance of providing college-level students with the skills need to explore career opportunities. Academy students need to be exposed to career investigation in their early coursework, via classroom exchanges, university career resources, and online sites, and real-world speakers. Career education is a lifelong learning experience that needs to have a greater focus from the first semester through the last for all university students.